

In Search of a Lost Capital: A Geo-archaeological Analysis of the Site-Debalgarh

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Abstract

In spite of its immense potential, Debalgarh archaeological site has been neglected through decades. It is evident from the Geo-archaeological investigations that as an advanced civilization it flourished over a vast area even before Gupta era. It is evident from the recovered archaeological objects that it was a centre of trade and commerce in ancient Bengal. A rural museum has been established to display and protect the recovered artefacts. Mass awareness has been developed. Palaeo-channels have been analysed and surveyed to reveal the Geo-archaeological importance of the site. Now the question arises- is present Debalgarh the past Sena capital 'Vijaypur'? Continuous research and scientific excavation are needed to unveil the untold information which may add a new chapter in the history of ancient Bengal.

Key Words: Debalgarh, Palaeo-channel, Ancient trade route

Introduction

Through the present paper an attempt has been made to represent an account of Geo-archaeological study of 'Debalgarh' and associated potential areas, located in the district of Nadia, West Bengal, India. An attempt has been made to identify the palaeo-channels and nature of landform evolution by field survey along with the understanding of chronology of civilisations through centuries by archaeological evidences.

Preamble:

'Debalgarh' or 'Debola' of 'Debagram gram panchayat' under Gangnapur police station and 'Anuliya Gram panchayat' under Ranaghat police station, Nadia district, can easily be described as a living archaeological site which is a neglected place through decades. Debalgarh archaeological site (along with Anulia and other adjacent spots) belongs to the trans-Bengal region at the interface of West Bengal and Bangladesh. The artifacts of the area date back to the eras as early as 3rd- 4th century, a period much prior to the Pre-Gupta era and shows evidence in the continuity of subsequent Gupta, Pala, Sena and Sultanate dynasties. The ruins of architectural structure also indicate that the site has been an immense potential centre of both administration and economics in the Pala-Sena era.

Spatial Location

The central location or the fort area of Debalgarh extends in an almost square pattern. Residual of four ancient earthen watch towers stand at four directions, covering almost one square km area. The latitudinal and longitudinal locations are following respectively:

NW: 23°9'38"N/88°39'17"E

NE: 23°9'50"N/88°39'55"E, SE: 23°9'16"N/88°40'5"E,

SW: 23°9'04.3"N/88°39'31.3"E respectively.

Debalgarhis nearly seventy five kilometres from Kolkata, located equidistant from Ranaghat and Chakdaha railway stations in Nadia district. Though this site can be identified as a binodal centre (Debagram and Anulia), thousands of artifacts have been unearthed within 10 to 15 kilometres radius area around Debalgarh. The central area of Debalgarh is located beside the palaeo-channel of river ' Marali'. The spot is much close and roughly eight kilometres away from the confluence of 'Marali' with river ' Ichhamati '.

Several spots with hundreds of artifacts have also been identified at Anulia Gram panchayat area under Ranaghat-I administrative block. The spots show a linear pattern allocation besides the palaeo-channel of river Ganga. The distance between Anulia and Debalgarh is less than ten kilometres in straight line distance. River 'Churni' flows from North-east to South-west direction towards Chakdaha to her confluence with Ganga.

Methodology

To asses properly the geo- archaeological importance, an extensive microlevel survey has been carried out through years. Primary survey has been carried out for both purposes- a) to study the nature geo- archaeological significance and recovered artefacts in general and b) to obtain the detailing of palaeo-channel analysis in particular. Both the paleo-channel of river Ganga at Anulia and Marali at Debagram have been analysed.

Different parameters like changes of slope, study of recovered organic substances from the dried up river bed, nature of sedimentation, study of soil texture from collected samples have been done. After receiving the data, the compilation and analysis have been conducted in post- field study. Location of palaeo-channels along the tributaries and distributaries, areas of archaeological findings has been plotted in maps to represent the spatial dimension.

Geo-archaeological Observations

Over the years, the evolution of the extinct river basin in the adjoining delta surrounding the Debalgarh archaeological site has been surveyed. The courses of rivers have changed and the process of delta formation has also evolved chronologically. The palaeochannels have been traced out through intensive field survey. The search was conducted across the region. Many important evidences of river based trade have been found. Several large sized blocks made of laterite stones were found from Debalgarh which were used to anchor large size boats and barges. Terracotta seals, anchoring stones, etc., prove conclusively that in ancient times the river Marali-Ichhamati flowing along the Debalgarh archaeological site and the Churni and Ganga flowing along the Anulia occupied a significant place in trade and commerce in ancient Bengal. Although the Ganges now flows through the western part of Nadia district, long-running geo- archaeological studies have shown that the location of the Ganges in ancient times was much different than it is today. Thousand years ago, the drainage system

and associated landforms of this Gangetic delta were quite different (Bagchi, 1944). Long ago, the river Ganga used to flow through the ancient town of 'Ula' or present-day Birnagar in Nadia district. It used to flow in ancient time the Anulia Gram Panchayat of today's Ranaghat Police Station. Field surveys across the villages of Anulia and Gurpara have been able to identify the extinct river basin of the Ganges. With the help of field survey, the extinct river basin has been identified and its extinct streams along with the present streams have been compiled on the map with the help of geographical information system (GIS). It is understood that the process of formation of the delta in this part of Central Bengal many centuries ago was like. It is understood how the drainage system of this region has been for many centuries. At the same time, field surveys on both sides of the palaeo channels have uncovered many archaeological specimens. By ensuring these, we are presented with a picture of an advanced civilization over a vast area that was flourished many centuries ago.

Establishment of Rural Museum

Despite its immense potential, the Debalgarh archaeological site is still waiting for extensive excavation and unfolding the complete history. In spite of continuous efforts taken, a few years ago, only but a few people knew about this archaeological site. Gradually, through systematic research and disclosure of information, Debalgarh is now appearing to the people. The information hidden under the jungle and mound is being revealed. Although numerous specimens have been found throughout the vast area over decades, one hardly cared about the research, excavation and presentation of the artifacts of this site. It is almost a decade ago that the mystery of Debalgarh has begun to unveil. From that time onwards, continuous research began and course of action has been commenced.

At first people suspected a lot and there have been many doubts. While conducting field surveys in villages, people have therefore looked at it with utter scepticism. For a long time, there has been an atmosphere of suspicion and mistrust in travel and mutual exchange. Mutual cooperation has gradually increased. The people of the village have come forward one by one to preserve the ancient culture. They have come forward to formulate the chapter of their lost history and heritage.

From the very beginning we believed that local people would be the pioneers in this work. By pushing the sediment of oblivion that has been lying on history for centuries, they will revive the trend of ancient history. Year after year has passed. One meeting after another with the villagers, the future course of action has been formulated through discussion. Finally, by the initiative of the local villagers, a rural museum has been set up at Debagram of Gangnapur police station in Nadia district, next to the Debalgarh archaeological site. Some of the villagers have left a part of their house, some have arranged a little furniture. People from all over Bengal, interested in archaeology, history, geography and folk culture have gradually flocked to this rural museum. Local farmers and villagers have donated their collected artefacts to the museum. All the artifacts are now carefully preserved in the rural museum today. Preserved for research, preserved for the future.

Today, the Debalgarh archaeological site is slowly gaining recognition on the history map of Bengal and India. Many experts have come. Officials of the Archaeological Department of the Government of West Bengal have arrived. Officials from Archaeological Survey of India have shown enthusiasm. The Asiatic Society has described Debalgarh as 'one of the major

archaeo- tourist destination in the map of Bengal' in their monthly magazine (The Asiatic Society, July 2018). Gradually, the importance of this archaeological site is becoming more and more apparent. Now all are waiting for scientific excavation and continuous research.

Selected Archaeological evidences

Remarkable archaeological specimens, recovered from multiple places of Debalgarh amaze us and draw our attention to a new avenue of possibility that has yet not been mentioned in conventional history. Along with other artifacts 'amphora' has been recovered (October, 2019) from the bank of river Churni flowing through Anulia gram panchayat of Ranaghat police station. This special type of pottery was supposed to be used in ancient times to transport wine, olive oil, pickles etc. According to expertise, throughout the second and third centuries, this special type of pottery produced by the fine clay of Bengal delta, was widely used for external trade. Most destinations were in various European countries, including Greece and Rome at the time.

It is not that single amphora has been discovered from a single place and thus, cannot be considered as a mere isolated discovery. The 'Parvati' canal in the Gopalnagar -Nahata area, adjacent to the Gangnapur police station, which connects the extinct river Jamuna with Churni; several amphoras along with other artifacts have also been found on the banks of that canal. The discovery of multiple amphoras, terracotta seal marks a significant addition so far as the archaeological history of ancient Bengal is concerned. Although various specimens of foreign trade including amphora have been found from the Chandraketugarh, Harinarayanpur archaeological site earlier (Sandhi Group, 2013) the discovery of such artefacts from the middle deltaic region of Nadia is a completely new phenomenon. Gold coins of the Gupta era have also been found from Debalgarh! Archer type gold coins or Dinar have been found where Gupta emperor Samudragupta marked standing with bow and arrow. It is found that in 1942, Binoy Chandra Sen in his book- "Historical Aspects of the Inscriptions of Bengal", writes about the receipt of Gupta era gold coins from (Sen, 1942) Debagram (Sen, 1942). Even today, though nearly hundred years have passed from the first reporting, inhabitants of Debalgarh have witnessed several gold coins of the Gupta period recovered from the depths during cultivation and constructional works. It is evident that with the passage of time, in the Gupta period, this region became one of the major centres of trade and commerce in the ancient Bengal.

In Search of a Lost Capital

Now the question arises about the identity of Debalgarh archaeological site. Evidence of the innumerable artefacts suggests that an advanced civilization developed here before the Gupta period. In the Gupta period this region became a developed centre of trade and commerce. Later, with gradual development this civilization reached its peak in the Pala and Sena eras. But who was the ruler? What was their identity? Why this huge arrangement of watch towers, double rampart and trench- (Moat?) surrounded fort? Why Debalgarh is featured with such a huge defence? Which time was Debalgarh established as a centre of immense power? These issues will be solved in the series of studies.

Through the multiple religious artefacts, terracotta seals, pottery, amphora, gold coins of Emperor Samudragupta found at different times from Debalgarh, the prosperity of trade and commerce in the Gupta period and earlier is quite evident. Debagram has been mentioned in ancient literature. It is known from the 'Ramcharit Manas ' by Sandhyakar Nandi that Raja Vikram Raj of Debagram was one of the few powerful feudal lords of Bengal who helped Rampal to suppress the Kaivarta rebellion during the reign of Pala Raja Rampal (Nandi, 1937). In other words, Devagram became a strong political and administrative centre during the Pala period. More and more research will reveal more new mysteries of history.

Debalgarh site is connected with one of the major controversies in history which has not been answered till date. We know about the capital of Sena, namely 'Vijaypur ' from the poem 'Pavandutam' written by Sena royal poet Dhoyi (Chakraborty, 1926). The Vijaypur was simultaneously the capital or administrative centre (Rajdhani) as well as the military centre (Skandhabar). But where was the capital Vijaypur located? Following the verses of the Pavandutam, we find that it was near Tribeni in today's Nadia district. The spatial location and the archaeological evidences discovered matches completely. Is Debalgarh, surrounded by ancient Ganges-Marali-Jamuna, the lost Sena capital Vijaypur? The location of Debalgarh is in complete agreement with the location of Vijaypur by the description of palaeo -channels and landform evolution analysis.

But is this the centre where Sena Raja Lakshmana Sena clashed with Sultan Bakhtiyar Khilji and defeated here? Did Laksmana Sena retreat to his capital Bikrampur? For a long time, there has been an idea of introducing Nabadwip as the capital of Sena. The Debalgarh archaeological site and its potential were not included in the discussion. The reason seems very simple and normal. No one knew the identity of this archaeological site, nor its features were revealed. Today it is clear that Bakhtiyar Khilji did not attack Nabadwip, Nabadwip was never the capital of Sena. It is found that, Acharya Jadunath Sarkar, Ramesh Chandra Majumdar in their texts clearly stated that Nabadwip was never the capital of Sena, but it was a pilgrimage centre on the banks of the Ganges (Sarkar, 1943; Majumder, 1971). Nabadwip has been known as a religious centre since ancient times. After the excavation of the Ballal mound by ASI, it became clear that it was not the capital centre but a Buddhist monastery primarily, which was later converted into a Hindu temple. No archaeological evidence has ever found in support of Sena capital at Nabadwip. In addition, it should be remembered also that at the time of the birth of Sri Chaitanyadev, Nabadwip was just a village. Several Chaitanya kavyas refer that Nabadwip was a remote village in time of the birth of Sri Chaitanya, neither a centre of trade nor the capital. If Nabadwip had been the ancient capital before the birth of Sri Chaitanya, its mention could have been found in any one of the texts.

We learn about the invasion of Bakhtiar Khilji from the main text of 'Tabakat-i-Nasiri ' by Minhaj. According to the text, Bakhtiyar Khilji attacked 'Nudiya Nagar', not Nabadwip (Raverty, 1873). Which centre was the attack the site or the then capital? It is clear, from the description of the text that at that time Nudiya Nagar was a fortified city. That city had city gates, walls, moats. It was a famous centre of trade and commerce (Roy, 1999). That is why Bakhtiyar disguised himself with his teammates easily as horse traders. None of this matches with Nabadwip. Rather, it coincides with the newly discovered Debalgarh. Now the question arises, is lost capital 'Vijaypur' hidden under the mounds of present Debalgarh site?

Conclusion

Archaeological evidences show that there is a huge potential hidden deep in this long neglected archaeological site. The excavation and proper research of this archaeological site can change the various ideas prevalent in history till date. If the information of this archaeological site is published properly, many conventional beliefs in the history of Bengal and India will change and the answers too many unknown questions will be found. The search is therefore awaiting the addition of a new chapter in the history of India and Bengal. This archaeological site is therefore needed proper scientific investigation for writing the unknown history of this region.

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Illustrations

LOCATION OF DEBALGARH-ANULIA ARCHAEOLOGICAL SITE

